

Investigations on synthesis, structural and magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles

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Abstract : Cobalt ferrite nanoparticles with different crystallite sizes have been synthesized using the coprecipitation method. In this work, the structure and phase purity was analyzed by using X-Ray diffraction (XRD). The compound analysis was done using the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX). The magnetic properties were studied using the vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). The magnetic crystalline anisotropy constant of CoFe_2O_4 was calculated using Law of Approach to Saturation (LAS) model. This plays a major role in the hyperthermia studies.

Keywords : X-Ray diffraction, SEM, EDAX, VSM.

Introduction

Ferrimagnetic spinel ferrite comprises a significant class of magnetic ceramics. They are mostly having cubic structure with magnetic and electrical properties depending on the nature and distribution of their cations in the two tetrahedral (A) and octahedral (B) sub lattices. Generally the spinel like cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) has a very high magnetocrystalline anisotropy and reasonable saturation magnetization¹. The magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite particles essentially depend on the size, shape and purity of these particles, which in turn are dependent on synthesizing these particles². The mixed spinel ferrite with general formula $[\text{A}_{1-x}^{2+}\text{B}_x^{3+}][\text{A}_x^{3+}\text{B}_{2-x}^{3+}]$ exhibits interesting physical properties which are having scope for applications in the field of magnetic resonance imaging contrast agents, data storage devices, transformer cores, magneto caloric refrigeration. When the size of the cobalt ferrite nanoparticles is reduced and becomes comparable to the single domain size, the spins are affected by the thermal fluctuations and they are found to exhibit superparamagnetic behavior with vanishing hysteresis loop and their coercivity approaches to zero³. The important properties of ferrite materials such as their high value of resistivity and low eddy current losses are very important for high frequency applications⁴. It is known that the crystal size is related to the relative interdependence between the nucleation and growth steps, which in

turn can strongly be affected by the solution chemistry and precipitation conditions⁵. The magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant was studied using "Law of approach to saturation". Since CoFe_2O_4 is growing up as a better candidate for hyperthermia agents, hence in the present investigation nanocrystalline cobalt ferrite particles were synthesized using coprecipitation method and its structural properties were studied with various sintering temperature. The magnetic properties of the sample annealed at 800 °C were studied. The magnetic crystalline anisotropy constant of the sample annealed at 800 °C was calculated using LAS and non linear curve fitting.

Results and discussion

Structural studies :

The X-ray diffraction was analyzed using Bruker D8 Advance. The Fig. 1 shows X-ray diffraction pattern of the cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) nanoparticles. The sample was annealed at 400 °C, 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C. The single phase of the CoFe_2O_4 was identified at 800 °C. The crystallite sizes were found to be 16.48, 20.11, 22.28, 27.50, 42.33 nm for 400 °C, 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C respectively. The crystallite size increased with increasing the annealing temperature. This may be attributed due to the fact that as the annealing temperature increases the crystallite size of the grain also increases. The crystallite size was calculated using

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of CoFe_2O_4 at different temperatures.

Scherrer equation with help of the most intense X-ray diffraction peak (311). The X-ray diffraction pattern was indexed using the JCPDS data (Card no. 22-1086).

Morphological studies :

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) with EDAX :

The SEM images were analyzed using JEOL model 6390. Fig. 2 shows the SEM image of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles annealed at 800 °C. The average particle size was found to be between 50–70 nm. The energy dispersive X-ray analysis was done for the sample annealed at 800 °C. The atomic weight percent of the elements present in the sample was determined by EDAX

Fig. 2. SEM with EDAX of sample annealed at 800 °C.

was found to be in agreement with the experimental ratios. The atomic weight percentages were found to be 16.96%, 30.88%, 52.17%, for cobalt, iron and oxygen elements respectively.

Magnetic studies :

Vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) :

The magnetic property of the sample was analyzed using Lakeshore VSM7410. The M-Hloop of the sample annealed at 800 °C is shown in the Fig. 3. The saturation magnetization (M_s), coercivity (H_c) and the magnetic moment were found to be 79.8 emu/g, 719 G and 3.334 μ_B respectively. The reported values were found to be in agreement in the reported values for cobalt ferrite⁴. Here “Law of Approach to Saturation” was used to calculate the magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant⁶. The magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant from “Law of approach to saturation” was found to be 0.66×10^6 .

Fig. 3. Hysteresis of the sample annealed at 800 °C.

Experimental

Nanocrystalline cobalt ferrite sample was prepared using coprecipitation method. Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and ferric nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with 99.9% purity were taken as precursor materials in the presence of alkaline medium. The ratio for cobalt to iron is found to be 1 : 2. The materials were dissolved in deionized water and were kept for continuous stirring. 8 M NaOH was added to the stirring solution, the particles were started to settle down. The

stirring was continued for two hours. The resultant solution was washed with ethanol and water in order to remove impurities. The final product was kept for drying at 80 °C. The dried sample was powdered using mortar and pestle and annealed at different temperatures in order to get the desired phase.

Conclusion

Nanocrystalline cobalt ferrites were synthesized by using coprecipitation method. The X-ray diffraction pattern was confirmed the CoFe_2O_4 . The sample was indexed using JCPDS data. The average particle size was found to be between 50–70 nm by using SEM. The elemental analysis was carried out by using EDAX and the result was in agreement with experimental ratios. The magnetic property was studied using vibrating sample magnetometer. Hysteresis loop was obtained by using VSM and different parameters were calculated. The saturation magnetization was found to be 79 emu/g which was close to the reported values. The coercivity was found to be 719 G. The magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant for the sample annealed at 800 °C was found to 0.66×10^6 . The value of magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant for

CoFe_2O_4 is 2.5×10^5 . The value of magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant plays a major role in the hyperthermia studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the management of VIT University, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India for constant support and encouragement. The authors are extremely thankful to Karunya University and IIT-SAIF for extending their help to obtain SEM with EDAX and VSM results.

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